

**STUDENT SATISFACTION WITH THE QUALITY OF HYBRID TEACHING IN THE EDUCATION
PROCESS OF THE DEPARTMENT OF HEALTH ECONOMICS**

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ABSTRACT

Education management is a driving force for education development. It requires constant innovation, but there are certain stages or periods, during which the need for changes becomes greater and more meaningful. The COVID-19 pandemic urgently stimulated innovation introduction in the educational sector. The hybrid teaching form is especially appropriate for medical university training.

The students' satisfaction with the teaching quality is an evaluation method which is hard and subjective. Their opinions on a variety of questions in regards to their training are important to its improvement. They are also important for the student's personal and professional development in the future.

The goal of this research is to study student satisfaction with the quality of hybrid teaching in the education process of the Department of Health Economics at the Faculty of Public Health “Prof. Tzekomir Vodenicharov, MD, DSc”, MU Sofia depending on the students' academic qualifications.

The following research methods were used: document method, sociological questionnaire survey, comparative analysis, medical and statistical method, table and graphic methods.

Based on the results obtained from the research we can conclude that over 85% of Master's students and ¾ of the Bachelors' are satisfied with the teaching methods and quality for all subjects in the Department of Health Economics.

Keywords: Innovations, quality, education process, student evaluation, hybrid teaching form.

Introduction

Education should be built on knowledge and new technology, which are the cardinal directions for national education strategy building in European Union member states. What stands out is the decisive role of technological innovation for the EU's turning into the most competitive economy. This is an economy based on knowledge, on the creation and implementation of

new products and technologies, of new production and social process management [4].

Education management is a driving force for education development. It requires constant innovation, but there are certain stages or periods, during which the need for changes becomes greater and more meaningful. [8]

The COVID-19 pandemic urgently stimulated innovation introduction in the educational sector. Digitalization and incorporation of technology in the classroom have been a subject of discussion for years. However, no one had anticipated them to become not only an additional element of the educational process, but the only way for it to be realized [5].

On the other hand, practical training, carried out in proximity to the sick, is a significant component of the education process in a medical university. The patient is a factor that inspires the future medical specialist to show respect and be as responsible as possible in realizing the therapeutical process. Without the patient, it is impossible for comprehensive professional development to occur in the future medical specialists. During practical training, the knowledge mastered by the students transforms into convictions, values, and the corresponding qualities, which present in their behavior. Independent and creative thinking, problem-solving, and the skills deriving benefit out of errors all form during seminars and practical classes [3]. An opportunity for effective communication and contacts is created [4].

When it comes to innovations, teaching is concentrated only on those aspects of educational work, which can easily be substituted with alternatives.

Teaching is defined as an information transfer process. Nowadays, students receive information via a few different pathways. They can gain knowledge at a time and place more suitable and convenient for them. Moreover, they can change the order of these pieces of information, so it is adapted to their motivation and interests. Students can individually dedicate as much times as they deem necessary for any thematic unit they find harder, or particularly interesting. They can also go through elements they find easy more quickly. Transfer flexibility is one of the most prospective education innovations [2].

Their opinions on a variety of questions in regards to their training are important to its improvement. They are also important for the student's personal and professional development in the future. [7].

Goal:

The goal of this research is to study student satisfaction with the quality of hybrid teaching in the education process of the Department of Health Economics at the Faculty of Public Health "Prof. Tzekomir Vodencharov, MD, DSc", MU Sofia depending on the students' academic qualifications.

Methodology:

The following research methods were used: document method, sociological questionnaire survey, comparative analysis, medical and statistical method, table and graphic methods.

In this article, we have presented a part of a wide survey encompassing 31 questions related to the organization and quality of hybrid training at the Department of Health Economics. The questionnaire was distributed to the respondents through the Google Forms platform in the June-October 2022 period.

Results and discussion

Respondent overview

309 students participated in the questionnaire. The majority of them (89.3%) are women, reflecting the fact that the students taught at the Faculty are predominantly women. The median age of the questionnaire respondents is 39 (IQR 27-45), whereas the youngest of them is 18, while the oldest is 56.

Four of every five participants (79.6%) are working towards a Bachelor's degree, whereas the remaining 20.4% are studying in a Master's program (Figure 1). Half of the students (50.2%) are in their first year, a third of them (31.4%) – in their second, and the remaining 18.4% - in their third.

Figure 1: Student distribution by degree.

The students in the Nursing specialty make the largest portion of participants (45.3%), followed by those in Public Health and Health Management (34%), Health Care Management (15.5%). The participation by students at the Midwifery (1.9%), Strategic Man-

agement in the Pharmaceutical Industry (1.9%), Occupational Health (1%), Medical Rehabilitation and Balneology (0.3%) specialties was not significant. No students from the Physician Assistant and Kinesiotherapy specialties participated.

Figure 2. Student distribution by specialty

Table 1.

Participant responses distribution by their satisfaction with the education process in the Department of Health Economics.

Questions	Possible Answers	Degree	
		Bachelor's	Master's
Are you satisfied with the teaching methods used in online lectures for different disciplines?	Yes, in all disciplines	73.2%	88.9%
	Yes, in some of the disciplines	25.2%	11.1%
	No, in no disciplines	1.6%	0.0%
Are you satisfied with the quality of material taught in online lectures?	Yes, in all disciplines	71.5%	85.7%
	Yes, in some of the disciplines	26.0%	14.3%
	No, in no disciplines	2.4%	0.0%
Do you receive timely information and help from your instructors in the classroom?	Yes, in all disciplines	79.3%	84.1%
	Yes, in some of the disciplines	18.7%	15.9%
	No, in no disciplines	2.0%	0.0%
Is lecture material published concurrently in the classroom and is it always available to the students?	Yes, in all disciplines	68.3%	84.1%
	Yes, in some of the disciplines	30.9%	15.9%
	No, in no disciplines	.8%	0.0%
In your opinion, do lecturers accentuate the key elements of the lecture during distance learning?	Yes, in all disciplines	76.4%	85.7%
	Yes, in some of the disciplines	22.0%	14.3%
	No, in no disciplines	1.6%	0.0%
Does the material taught in class correspond to the syllabus requirements/ list of exam topics?	Yes, in all disciplines	80.1%	81.0%
	Yes, in some of the disciplines	18.3%	19.0%
	No, in no disciplines	1.6%	0.0%
Are enough appropriate resources (textbooks, workbooks, manuals, online resources) provided to aid in acquiring the study material?	Yes, in all disciplines	74.4%	85.7%
	Yes, in some of the disciplines	23.6%	14.3%
	No, in no disciplines	2.0%	0.0%

Table 1 makes it visible that the students at large are satisfied with the methods used to teach the material in online lectures for a given discipline. When it comes to the student's degree, a larger percentage of Master's students is satisfied – 88.9%, followed by the Bachelor's students at 73.2%. ¼ of Bachelor's students and only 11.1% of the Master's students find the teaching methods satisfactory in in a part of their disciplines. There are also Bachelor's students who aren't satisfied with the methods used to teach the material in online lectures in any of the disciplines.

And to the question "Are you satisfied with the quality of lecture material taught in distant learning classes?" the relative portion of Master's students who

are satisfied with the material in all lectures is 85.7%, with the Bachelor's students at 71.5%. Again, ¼ of Bachelor's students report being satisfied only in a part of the disciplines, and 2.4% aren't satisfied with the quality of the lecture material taught in any disciplines.

The distribution of the answers of the question "Do you receive timely information and help from your instructors in the classroom?" is similar, but it can be observed that the answers of the Bachelor's and Master's students are slightly closer.

According to 84.1% of Master's students the lecture material for all disciplines is published concurrently in the classroom and is always available to the students, while 68.3% of Bachelor's students share this

opinion and 30.9% report that this is the case in only some disciplines.

Yet again, the percentage of Master's student respondents who say that lecturers accentuate the key elements of the lecture during distance learning in almost all disciplines - 85.7%. As little as 14.3% report that this is the case only for some disciplines. 76.4% of the Bachelor's students gave a positive response to this question for all disciplines, and 22% for a part of the disciplines. According to 1.6% this statement doesn't apply to any disciplines.

CONCLUSION

Reforms in the Bulgarian higher education system are developing in the political context of the current reforms in the European Higher Education Area. European criteria for modernizing higher education are being introduced with the aim of guaranteeing the quality of the offered education.

It is not only important that medical specialists acquire scientific knowledge and get acquainted with new technology. They also need to acquire the skills and attitudes for working properly in terms of practice, to be in step with the give social and health policy, with the quality standards and the patients' health insurance. [2]

The question of effectively schooling specialists, so that they obtain high quality specialized training is a primary concern for the teaching staff at the Department of Health Economics at the Faculty of Public Health "Prof. Tzekomir Vodenicharov, MD, DSc".

Based on the data obtained in this research, we have reached the conclusion that over 85% of Master's and $\frac{3}{4}$ of Bachelor's students are satisfied with the teaching methods and quality in all disciplines at the Department of Health Economics at the Faculty of Public Health "Prof. Tzekomir Vodenicharov, MD, DSc".

The results of the conducted research are, to a large degree, dependent on the participation of the students who are taught in the educational process, by their motivation, diligence and the effort they put in their work. The organization and conducting of educational

activity aimed at obtaining theoretical knowledge and practical skills is also important.

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